

Numerical tools for simulating low-energy electron interactions in experimental nanodosimetry applications

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ABSTRACT

Radiation damages to genes and cells occur at the DNA level, and therefore they are directly related to the spatial distribution of events caused by radiation at nanometer scale. Nanodosimetry introduces new quantities to correlate the initial features of radiation interactions and the likelihood of late radiobiological effects by means of Monte Carlo codes and, experimentally, with gas-detectors operating at low pressure.

Within this context, the aim of this work is to develop a numerical approach based on the implementation of different simulation tools to accurately describe the low energy electron transport processes within nanodosimetric devices. This approach was directly applied to perform a proof-of-concept study of the response of the electron collector of the STARTRACK nanodosimeter. Garfield++ was used to simulate the primary track structure of 5.8 MeV He-4 particles, while COMSOL Multiphysics was used to model the geometry and the electrostatic field of the electron collector. Available experimental data, measured with the STARTRACK nanodosimeter, were used to validate Garfield++ nanodosimetric spectrum before proceeding with the simulation of the electron transport stage in the drift volume, again performed with Garfield++. In order to verify the performance and reliability of the implemented codes, the nanodosimetric distributions were studied with the threefold objective of characterizing the time, space, and energy distributions of particles collected at the end of the drift volume. These results can offer a valuable insight into the overall working principle of nanodosimeters: this understanding can be pivotal in optimizing and refining the design of such devices, ultimately extending their effectiveness in particle track characterization during radiation therapy.

1. Introduction

Radiation-induced damages are strongly correlated to the ionization pattern induced by a charge particle within critical subcellular structures (Goodhead, 1994; Colautti et al., 2020). In such volumes, the physical processes of energy deposition have a discrete and stochastic nature, thus require appropriate quantities that can be measurable and that can quantify the induction of biological effects. Nanodosimetry originates to describe the track structure of primary particles, through the analysis of the number ν of ionizations produced inside a sensitive target in coincidence with the passage of each primary particle. The value ν represents the basic quantity of nanodosimetry, and it is called ionization cluster size. Since its value is dominated by the stochastic nature of the ionization process induced by the radiation, the cluster size is characterized by a frequency distribution, called ionization cluster

size distribution (ICSD) (De Nardo et al., 2002).

Experimentally, nanometric sites of tissue-equivalent matter are reproduced through the principle of simulation, by filling millimetric sensitive volumes with gas at low pressure. Their dimensions of mass per area should be similar to those of liquid water, assumed as a substitute to sub-cellular tissues, to simulate approximately the same mechanisms of radiation interaction (Grosswendt et al., 2004; Bantsar et al., 2017; Bortot et al., 2020; Mazzucconi et al., 2020a).

Currently, four different detection systems have been developed worldwide to perform experimental nanodosimetry. Three devices are based on ion-counting techniques: the FIRE (Frequency of Ion Registration) counter at the University of Zürich (Vasi et al., 2021), the Ion Counter installed at the Physikalisch-Technische Bundesanstalt in Germany (Garty et al., 2002), and the Jet Counter developed at the National Centre for Nuclear Research in Poland (Pszona et al., 2000). Instead, the

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STARTRACK Counter at the Legnaro National Laboratories of the National Institute of Nuclear Physics is based on the counting of low-energy electrons (De Nardo et al., 2002).

The STARTRACK measurement process involves four main stages: the ionizing particle crosses a gas-filled interaction chamber at a distance d from the sensitive volume of defined shape and size and reaches a trigger detector. Low-energy electrons directly produced by the primary particle or by its secondaries within the target volume are collected by means of an electron collector, that transfers them from the interaction chamber to the drift column, where they are ultimately detected by a multi-step avalanche chamber (MSAC). It should be noted that the STARTRACK nanodosimeter is a bulky and fixed experimental apparatus installed along a research accelerator beamline. In many different works, Monte Carlo codes (e.g. Geant4-DNA) have been exploited for simulating the ICSD of charged particles and for studying the response of nanodosimeters (Pietrzak et al., 2021; Hilgers et al., 2022). The exploitation of such track-structure codes gives the possibility to validate the different models (e.g. low-energy electron cross sections) exploited for the low energy region of the particle interactions. The cited works demonstrated that the combination of ICSD models and measurements are of undeniable relevance for the development of new detectors. Nevertheless, the implemented Monte Carlo codes are not specifically designed for considering the effect of an electric field distribution on the collected electrons or ions. Moreover, the simulations are generally focused on the resultant ICSD and not on the physical phenomena during the charge collection phase. For this reason, the development of new codes (Mazzucconi et al., 2020b) or the investigation of existing ones could be beneficial for the design of new detectors.

The aim of this paper is to present and discuss different numerical tools which can be exploited for describing the physics related to the working principle of a nanodosimeter based on the collection of the electrons. Through the exploitation of adequate numerical tools, a deeper understanding of the operational principles of such devices can be gained, leading to the development of higher-performance track-detectors that can, in the future, applied at the clinical level for radiation quality characterization in particle therapy. As a proof-of-concept, this work specifically focuses on describing the electron transport within the electron collector of the STARTRACK nanodosimeter.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Simulation strategy

The numerical study of the track structure generation and electron collection process was achieved by means of different numerical tools,

which allowed to model the complete primary particle and secondary electrons histories. Starting from the generation in the sensitive volume, the electron path was followed in a reference drift volume till electrons were either being absorbed by the electrodes or reached the surface at the end of the counter, called now on collection surface.

As benchmark, this methodology was applied for the evaluation of the performance of an electron counter based on the STARTRACK electron collector. The schematic operating principle of the nanodosimeter is presented in Fig. 1.

The design of the electron collector and the detailed simulation of the electrostatic field configuration was performed with COMSOL Multiphysics, a software platform for multiphysics simulations with dedicated physical interfaces and tools for the modelling of AC/DC electromagnetics in 2D or 3D (COMSOL, 2022), while the particle track structure in the sensitive volume and the dynamic electron transport within the electron collector, when subjected to the external electric field, were computed using the particle tracking software Garfield++ (GARFIELD++, 2023).

COMSOL and Garfield++ have been chosen because they have a communication interface, therefore, even a complex electric field defined by the finite element simulation can be imported in the Garfield++ environment. Moreover, since Garfield++ can rely on detailed collision-by-collision particle models for gases in presence of an electric field, it has been selected for carrying out the electron generation and transport into the simulated nanodosimeter. More details on the Garfield++ physical models are described in the following sections. The flow diagram of the simulation strategy is highlighted in Fig. 1, right side.

2.2. Electron collector geometry

The Monte Carlo simulations were performed for He-4 particles from a ^{244}Cm source, considered monoenergetic, whose most probable energy is about 5.8 MeV, for a total of 10^5 histories. The considered target site was a cylinder of 1 cm in diameter and 1 cm in height with the main axis perpendicular to the beam direction. The filling-gas was pure propane at temperature of 25 °C and 1 mbar in pressure. The equivalent simulated site is 18.25 nm when scaled at unit density. Moreover, an additional simulation has been carried out for monoenergetic alpha particles at energy equal to 1.47 MeV. Their behaviour is of primary importance in the development of boron neutron capture therapy for the treatment of cancer and other diseases, thus the track-structure needs to be studied at nanometric level.

A simplified model of the nanodosimeter was defined by reproducing the geometry adopted in the STARTRACK counter (De Nardo et al.,

Fig. 1. Left side: Schematic view of the measuring principle of the electron generation and collection process. The low-energy electrons produced by each primary particle within the sensitive volume (in orange) are transferred to a collection surface (in blue), via an electron collector, where they are detected. Right side: schematic diagram of the simulation strategy.

2002a,b). The work has been focused on the cone of the electron collector of the nanodosimeter and, therefore, other additional electrodes have been neglected; the drift volume was defined by eight ring electrodes, each 1.67 mm in height and spatially separated by 5 mm. The lower electrode (which acts as a cathode) has a diameter equal to the sensitive volume, which measures 1 cm. To enhance electron confinement within the drift volume, two additional equidistant ring electrodes were positioned between the cathode and the cone, as stated by De Nardo et al. (2002a,b). The geometric representation of the setup is illustrated in Fig. 2. The cathode and the rings were initially set at 0 V, while potential values ranging from 10 V to 80 V were assigned to the cone electrodes. The cone-shaped drift volume has already proven to be effective in the focusing of electrons, since its design gives rise to an electric field with a strong vertical component above the sensitive volume and minimizes the electron absorption and secondary emission from the electrodes (De Nardo et al., 2002a,b).

2.3. Electron generation and transport

Garfield++ is a powerful software package for the microscopic simulations of particles detectors based on ionization in gases or semiconductors (GARFIELD++, 2023). Garfield++ relies on several classes and functions employed for the definition of the chamber, the gas composition and the models used for the treatment of electron/ion transport (Schindler, 2023).

For the purpose of this work, the TrackHeed class was employed for the simulation of the primary particle track structure. This class allows to simulate ionization patterns produced by charged particles traversing the gaseous sensitive volume: after primary particle initialization, the clusters produced along the track are recorded for reproducing the nanodosimetric distribution for the different primary ions.

The program Heed is an implementation of the photo-absorption ionization (PAI) model which is based on the relation between the energy deposited by the fast charged particle in a medium and the photoabsorption cross-section of this medium. This model demonstrated its applicability for the research and development of gaseous detectors of fast charged particles (Smirnov, 2005). The transport threshold of the

primary charged particles has been set equal to 1 keV in kinetic energy, while the electron cut in this first step (TrackHeed) is set equal to the minimum ionization energy of propane (10 eV) for preventing endless diffusion of particles.

The ionization pattern has been simulated in a wider volume with respect to the sensitive one for considering the contribution of δ -rays originating outside the sensitive region.

It should be noted that Garfield++ was not originally designed as code for nanodosimetry; for this reason, the simulated cluster distribution was compared to experimental data measured by the STARTRACK counter (Bortot et al., 2022), to test the reliability of the models exploited in the code.

Once the primary particle track-structure was defined, the transport stage within the electron collector could be addressed. Starting from the geometry defined, the drift volume was filled with propane gas in the studied conditions of temperature and pressure, while electrodes and the cathode were constituted by an ideal conductive material. Once the geometry and the materials were defined, boundary conditions, such as charge conservation and initial values of electrodes voltage, were set to determine the area where Maxwell equations had to be solved (Kempf et al., 2022). The electric field and the mesh data were then exported to Garfield++ for the modelling of electron trajectories. A material-mapping file containing the material properties was also needed to connect the COMSOL domains to the respective material regions in Garfield++ (Kempf, 2021).

The electron transport simulation was performed with the tracking method implemented in the class AvalancheMicroscopic in Garfield++ (Schindler, 2023). In addition to the geometry and electric field specifications, the simulation required multiple input parameters, such as the starting position of the electrons to be transported, and the pressure, temperature and chemical composition of the drift medium. Electron transport properties were defined by the MAGBOLTZ program, that computes the transport properties of electrons in a gas mixture under the influence of electric and magnetic fields, such as drift velocity, diffusion, gain and attachment, through the numerical integration of Boltzmann transport equations (Biagi, 2021). More in details, the AvalancheMicroscopic electron transport relies on the electron-atom/molecule cross-sections in the database of the Magboltz program (Biagi, 1999). During the simulation, any primary and secondary electron is followed by exploiting a collision-based approach, down to zero energy.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Garfield++ cluster size distribution: primary particle track

The nanodosimetric spectra along the track obtained from Garfield++ simulations are shown in Fig. 3: the distributions have a strongly peaked shape at a maximum cluster size that depends on the radiation ionization density.

Table 1 summarizes the conditions studied and the mean number of ionizations produced within the target M_1 , defined as:

$$M_1 = \sum_{\nu=0}^{\infty} \nu P_{\nu}(Q, d)$$

Where ν are the number of ionizations produced in the target volume and $P_{\nu}(Q, d)$ is defined as the probability of having a cluster size equal to ν for a radiation quality Q (i.e. particle energy and type) crossing the considered volume at a distance d from its center (defined as impact parameter).

This value shows the high clustering degree and complexity of the biological damages that can be induced by the primary ionizing particles.

Fig. 2. Geometry of the electron collector implemented in COMSOL Multiphysics. The sensitive volume is highlighted in red.

Fig. 3. ICSDs for 5.8 MeV He-4 particles (blue line) and 1.47 MeV He-4 particles (orange line) crossing the sensitive volume.

Table 1

Summary of the radiation qualities studied. The simulations are performed at impact parameter $d = 0$.

	E [MeV]	Site [nm]	M_1
He-4	5.8	18.25	52.5
He-4	1.47	18.25	161.0

3.2. Garfield++ cluster size distribution: comparison with STARTRACK counter

To assess whether the model implemented in Garfield++ is suitable for describing the particle track structure in nanometric volumes, the cluster size probabilities calculated along the track were compared with the corresponding cluster size distribution measured by the STARTRACK counter and reported in (Bortot et al., 2022). In order to directly compare the distributions, it is essential to take into account that the STARTRACK nanodosimeter is characterized by a collection efficiency that depends on the local electric field, thus on the point where each electron is produced: this results in a higher probability of collecting electrons produced near the electron collector, decreasing significantly toward the borders. In the STARTRACK counter the spatial dependence of the efficiency is defined by an efficiency map with radial symmetry, calculated by means of Monte Carlo simulations.

Experimentally, the reduced cluster distribution $\tilde{P}_v(Q, d, \varepsilon)$ and ‘true’ distribution $P_\mu(Q, d, \varepsilon = 1)$, where ε is the collection efficiency, obtained along the track are related through a binomial relationship which accounts for the differences in shape due to the non-uniform detection efficiency by considering only an average value $\bar{\varepsilon}$ (De Nardo et al., 2002):

$$\tilde{P}_v(Q; d; \bar{\varepsilon}) = \sum_{\mu=v}^{\infty} \binom{\mu}{v} \bar{\varepsilon}^v (1 - \bar{\varepsilon})^{\mu-v} P_\mu(Q; d)$$

The ‘reduced’ efficiency in STARTRACK for He-4 particles is around 0.16 (Bortot et al., 2022), but in the following analysis it is scaled to 0.18 to consider the different sizes of the simulated site (20.6 nm for STARTRACK, 18.25 nm for the sensitive volume under study). This efficiency adjustment is undeniable for performing a comparison with experimental data from the nanodosimeter.

Additionally, a dead-time correction must be applied to take into account the non-negligible time resolution of the detector, which has the capability to distinguish and count separately electrons with a resolving

time of $\tau = 30$ ns.

Fig. 4 presents the comparison between the reduced cluster size distribution \tilde{P}_v of 5.8 MeV He-4 simulated with Garfield++ and the corresponding nanodosimetric spectrum measured by STARTRACK.

The agreement between the calculated nanodosimetric spectra and the experimental distribution is considered satisfactory, as there is only a slight deviation noticed at higher cluster sizes. To gain a comprehensive understanding of the underlying cause of this discrepancy, a thorough analysis of the cross-section models implemented in the software is warranted and comparisons by exploiting different particles and energies should be carried out. Nevertheless, for the purpose of this work the cluster distribution generated by the simulation proved to be adequate in describing the ionization density of the primary particle. Therefore, the simulation of the collection phase within the drift volume can be carried out, building on the promising foundation established by the nanodosimetric spectra agreement.

3.3. COMSOL multiphysics: electric field simulation

Between the different possible applications, COMSOL can be used for the calculation of electrostatic fields through the dedicated Electrostatics (es) interface under the AC/DC module (COMSOL, 2022). Starting from the geometry described in Section 2.2, the resulting electric field along the xz plane is shown in Fig. 5. The resulting electric field has a broadening effect on the spatial distribution of electrons, as they diffuse from the sensitive volume through the drift electrodes.

Further analyses of the transport phenomena in the electron collector were carried out by modifying the voltage range of the electrodes, from 20 V to 160 V and from 30 V to 240 V, keeping a 20 V step and a 30 V step between electrodes, respectively. In this way, the configuration of the field lines of the electric field remains unchanged, the electrons are only subjected to higher potential differences that accelerate them at higher energies. This will be crucial in determining the electron trajectory and the contribution of secondary ionizations produced in the transport stage. It should be underlined that, in order to maximise the electron collection capability, the exact voltage values should be investigated with a more detailed analysis that will be matter of future work.

3.4. Garfield++ cluster size distribution: transport stage

In the Garfield++ transport process, each electron was placed at a

Fig. 4. Reduced cluster size probability distribution \tilde{P}_v of 5.8 MeV He-4 ions from Garfield++ simulation (blue line) and the corresponding cluster size distribution P_v measured with STARTRACK (orange line).

Fig. 5. Electric potential resulting from electrostatic COMSOL calculations. Only the electric field between 0 and 80 V is shown, since the configurations of the other fields are the same but the voltage range. This view is a cross-section view of Fig. 2 on the cone axis.

specific starting position (calculated as described in section 2.3) and transported in the gaseous medium until it was either lost by impacting on the electrodes or exited the reference volume. The final coordinates, the travelling time and the final energy of all the simulated particles were considered. Among them, only the electrons that reach the collection surface at the end of the drift volume were analyzed in terms of space and time distributions, together with their energy spectrum.

As already mentioned in Section 3.1, electron transport properties are locally defined as a function of the applied electric field and of its gradient. Because of the strong inhomogeneity of the electric field in the electron collector, the local collection efficiency in the sensitive volume is not constant. However, an average value can be defined to correlate the original distribution and the reduced nanodosimetric distribution by applying the same procedure described in section 3.2.

The mean collection efficiency was calculated as the fraction of collected electrons with respect to the total number of electrons generated along the primary track. Since particle-particle and particle-field interactions, i.e. space charge effects, are not considered in the Garfield++ simulations, the average collection capability of the device does not depend on the cluster dimensions of the primary radiation.

The ionization cluster size distribution of the collected electrons at the end of the transport stage was compared to the original distribution, generated along the track, to verify that the distributions obtained from the present simulations are effectively correlated, and thus keep the same physical information.

For this comparison, the true distribution was scaled with the binomial relation with the corresponding mean collection efficiency, listed in Table 2. Figs. 6 and 7 show the comparison of the ICSD for 5.8 MeV and 1.47 MeV He-4 particles, respectively. A very good agreement was achieved between the distributions.

Table 2 reports, for the considered radiation qualities, the reduced mean cluster size \tilde{M}_1 compared to the true mean number of primary ionizations produced along the primary track M_1 . The value of \tilde{M}_1 scales approximately with M_1 , after a correction for the average collection

Table 2

Mean cluster size \tilde{M}_1 calculated from the Garfield++ cluster size distribution after the transport stage.

	E[MeV]	M_1	\tilde{M}_1	$\bar{\epsilon}$
He-4	5.8	52.5	17.23	0.328
He-4	1.47	161.0	53.15	0.330

Fig. 6. Reduced cluster size probability distribution \tilde{P}_v of 5.8 MeV He-4 ions, scaled for the corresponding reduced collection efficiency (blue line) and cluster size distribution at the collection surface, after Garfield++ dynamic electron tracking (orange line).

Fig. 7. Reduced cluster size probability distribution \tilde{P}_v of 1.47 MeV He-4 ions, scaled for the corresponding reduced collection efficiency (blue line) and cluster size distribution at the collection surface, after Garfield++ dynamic electron tracking (orange line).

efficiency, as:

$$\tilde{M}_1(Q, d, \epsilon) = \bar{\epsilon} M_1$$

3.5. Time analysis

Big clusters have a higher probability that two electrons reach the collection surface within a time interval shorter than the detector resolving time, giving rise to overlapping signals that cannot be distinguished as separate events. In a miniaturized device made only by the electron collector, this problem is particularly critical because electrons do not have enough space to diffuse longitudinally and to be separated in time like in the drift column of the STARTRACK nanodosimeter, thus very fast detector should be employed.

Therefore, a temporal analysis could be useful to examine how the resolution time influences the shape of the cluster-size distributions. The

probability distribution obtained for 5.8 MeV He-4 particle is shown in Fig. 8, considering that the collection surface has a resolving time of 30, 10 and 0 ns. It should be noted that 30 ns is the resolving time of the STARTRACK nanodosimeter, as discussed before. The shapes of the ICSDs are clearly compressed at larger cluster sizes, causing the loss of much of the initial information about the number of primary ionizations that occurs in the sensitive volume. Higher losses are expected for 1.47 He-4 ions since it is a higher LET particle (Fig. 9).

These results mean that the temporal separation (i.e. detector resolving time) of the electron paths is a fundamental parameter for correctly measuring the dimension of the cluster sizes.

3.6. Space analysis

In the simulated nanodosimeter, composed by the electron collector only, electron counting based on temporal discrimination results in a great distortion in the measured ionization cluster size distribution, especially for densely ionizing particles. Due to the relevance of pile-up effects, distributions are strongly modified, which makes it difficult to trace them back to the original distributions. This operation can be done by considering a single parameter represented by the detector collection efficiency, which can be highly modified by the electric field configuration. The correct estimation of this parameter is of fundamental importance for, e.g., the comparison of the STARTRACK distributions with other nanodosimeters. For this reason, also the spatial pattern of the electrons in the device was studied through simulations. This analysis allowed to study two different aspects of the transport phenomena: 1) the influence of the electric field configuration on the spatial behavior of electrons as they diffuse in the drift volume, and 2) the contribution of secondary ionization events induced by the primary electrons impacts on the cluster-size distribution P_v . The latter is critical to assess whether the measured probability distribution does not lose its physical meaning during the electron collection phase.

The simulation of electrons trajectories in the collector was performed for the 5.8 MeV He-4 particle dataset at different electric potential configurations. In the computed set-ups the cathode and the ring electrodes were kept at 0 V, while the maximum voltage of the conelectrode was set respectively at 80 V, 160 V and 240 V. The electron trajectories are almost exclusively determined by elastic scattering events, so the resulting spatial distribution has a cylindrical symmetry. The main consequences of the potential change on the spatial

Fig. 8. Nanodosimetric spectra of 5.8 MeV He-4 particles obtained considering pile-up losses at the detector level for a resolving time of 0 ns (blue line), 10 ns (orange line) and 30 ns (yellow line). The shape of the distribution is deformed at high cluster sizes if a larger time threshold is set.

Fig. 9. Nanodosimetric spectra of 1.47 MeV He-4 particles obtained considering pile-up losses at the detector level for a resolving time of 0 ns (blue line), 10 ns (orange line) and 30 ns (yellow line). The extend of the losses is more pronounced due to the higher ionization density of 1.47 MeV He-4 ions.

distribution were a focusing effect for electrons, which is stronger the higher is the voltage range, and an increase in the mean collected electrons, due to secondary electron production.

At the highest electric potential, electrons underwent greater acceleration, whereby the contribution of ionization processes became more relevant and multiple secondary electrons were produced within the drift volume. The probability distributions P_v obtained for different collector potentials are compared and reported in Fig. 10. The green and purple line refer to the original nanodosimetric distributions scaled for the average collection efficiency, obtained respectively for 0–160 V and 0–240 V. For each dataset, the mean collection efficiency was calculated from the total number of electrons reaching the collection surface with respect to the total number of electrons produced along the primary track: at potential range of 0–160 V the efficiency is 0.35, while at the higher potential condition, 0–240 V, the efficiency value reaches 0.56 due to the gas multiplication influence in the drift stage.

Fig. 10. Cluster size probability distributions for 5.8 MeV He-4 particles in different potential ranges: range 0–80 V (broken blue line), range 0–160 V (orange line), range 0–240 V (yellow line). The triangles refer to the original distribution rescaled with the reduced collection efficiency, respectively of 0.35 (green triangle) and 0.56 (purple triangle).

At higher potential, the distributions shift towards larger cluster sizes, as expected, but are still in agreement with the original distribution, properly scaled. Therefore, the electric field configuration in the electron collector should ensure a high collection efficiency and a small contribution of secondary ionizations in the drift volume to not distort the shape of the simulated probability distribution P , with respect to the true one. The exact voltage value of the collector electrodes (which are not available for this work) should be investigated more in detail to fulfil all the requirements. Finally, it should be noted that the estimated efficiencies take into account the cone collector only and not the drift column which may further impact on the reduction of the counted electrons.

3.7. Energy spectrum

For developing and studying new nanodosimeters and new strategies for single electron counting the energy spectrum of the collected electrons plays a key role. For 0–80 V potential condition at pressure of 1 mbar, the final energy of the electrons does not exceed few eVs, as shown in Fig. 11 (blue line). It is interesting to notice that even by increasing the potential, the increase on the electron energy is limited by the elastic scattering processes and, for higher potential values, by the generation of secondary electrons during the drift process. On the collector region, the percentages of the electrons which remains above the minimum propane ionization energy (around 11 eV) are 0.083%, 1.619% and 2.673% for 0–80 V, 0–160 V and 0–240 V, respectively. This values can give a first rough indication of the probability of charge multiplication in the collector.

4. Conclusion

In this work, a novel numerical framework has been investigated for analyzing nanodosimetric cluster size distributions and the response of a portion of a real nanodosimeter. The developed computational tools composed by COMSOL Multiphysics and the Garfield++ Monte Carlo code have been exploited for simulating the transport of low energy electrons in the collector cone of the STARTRACK nanodosimeter.

The results show that the Garfield++ software is capable of simulating cluster size distribution for He-4 particles for 18 nm in simulated site size when compared to experimental data. This result encourages further comparison for different particles, energies and simulated site sizes.

The simulated device can give a consistent characterization of the He-4 particles track structure at propane pressure of 1 mbar, for different radiation qualities. The ionization cluster size distributions evaluated from the collected electrons can be traced back to the original distributions, calculated along the track, and therefore maintain the same physical information about the potential biological damage of the primary radiation.

The simulations give both time discrimination and a spatial tracing of the transported electrons, which are fundamental for the design of low energy electron counting detectors. The simulations shows that the selection of the electrodes voltages is critical to assure a good broadening of electrons and to minimize the contribution of secondary ionizations to not distort the nanodosimetric spectrum. Finally, the energy spectra obtained under all conditions of pressure extend up to a few tens of eV. For example, an *ad-hoc* detection system should be addressed in future studies, so that experimental results can be obtained for validating those hitherto simulated.

It should be noted that this work has been focused on the investigation of numerical tools for the transport of low energy electrons by considering the design of the STARTRACK nanodosimeter as benchmark; in this way a first proof-of-concept study have been carried out. Nevertheless, further comparison between experimental results and simulations will be matter of future work. Moreover, even if this work has been focused on a small and simplified portion of a nanodosimeter,

Fig. 11. Energy spectra of the collected electrons at different potential ranges: 0–80 V (blue line), 0–160 V (green line) and 0–240 V (purple line).

the same numerical approach could be exploited for the simulation of more complex detectors and for designing, e.g., other collection geometries which can improve the performance of a nanodosimeter.

Finally, it should be noted that the numerical framework developed in this work could be further expanded and applied to other existing nanodosimeters like the FIRE detector (Vasi et al., 2021). The COMSOL and Garfield++ numerical tools described in this work could fit the thick-GEM approach, on which this nanodosimeter is based on, since the cited Monte Carlo code has been extensively used for GEM simulations (Schindler, 2023).

CRedit authorship contribution statement

C. Caprioli: Writing – original draft, Software, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **D. Mazzucconi:** Writing – original draft, Supervision, Methodology, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **D. Bortot:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Conceptualization. **S. Agosteo:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition. **A. Pola:** Supervision, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **D. Rastelli:** Writing – review & editing, Resources, Project administration, Funding acquisition. **N. Protti:** Writing – review & editing, Project administration, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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